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Transformation of the Scientific System of Ukraine During the 1990s

A reality of world civilization development today is the formation of a new type of society based on knowledge and information. Steady economic growth of any state is only possible provided the corresponding development of science, technology and innovation. And intellectual potential is the primary factor that determines harmony between human development and increased welfare.

This year Ukraine celebrated the tenth anniversary of its independence. During the past ten years Ukraine has made giant steps in its political, social, cultural and economic development. This can be seen by the fact that today, Ukraine has considerable productive and intellectual potential and has seen world-class achievements in some branches of industry and basic and applied science. And Ukraine's cultural sphere is based on millennial traditions of one of the most ancient peoples of the world.

Development of a new scientific system

In Ukraine over the past 10 years, as in other states of the former Soviet Union, a complicated process is taking place of institutional, structural and cognitive changes in the scientific system. Under the Soviet system, science was administered by the state and tightly organized. The establishment of a new scientific system, organized and financed in a sovereign state under the conditions of transition to a market economy and democratic principles of government, is proceeding slowly.

There are two main reasons for this slow transition. First, is a deep economic crisis, which during the rather short period of the existence of a "New Ukraine" has resulted in economic losses comparable to those Ukraine suffered in the second World War. During Soviet times, Ukrainian science was subsidized by the state and benefited from a large military R&D budget. The loss of state subsidies and cuts in military spending have had a severe impact on Ukrainian science.

The second reason that the transition to a new scientific system has been slower than expected has been the general societal aversion to fast, radical changes and new mechanisms. This reluctance to change has been seen in politics in the transfer from totalitarianism to democracy; in economics from state control to market control; and in science from state-administered research to independence, sustainability, and commercialization. Thus, in a system-wide social and economic crisis, Ukrainian science found itself among the social spheres that suffered major losses.

In the past decade, the number of researchers in Ukraine has dropped to half its former number, while funding has decreased almost by a factor of ten. The basic indicators of scientific activity in Ukraine -- i.e. the number of publications, patents, research projects, implemented innovations -- have decreased correspondingly. Part of the scientific elite emigrated (about 6,000 scientists) to countries with better conditions for science and technology: first and foremost, to Russia, the USA, Germany and Israel. The emigration of scientists was accompanied by a rapid aging of scientific personnel due to young researchers leaving the field and an inadequate inflow of new young scientists.

Nevertheless, some scientific branches in Ukraine have seen their potential not only maintained, but even strengthened. This is seen in the existence of scientific schools, well-known all over the globe, in particular, in mathematics, decimeter radio astronomy, physiology and cellular biology, low-temperature physics, materials, biotechnologies, and electric welding. Ukraine's continuing scientific potential is also seen in the development of new unique technologies, specifically, in the branch of informatics, telecommunications and communication. We can expect the fulfillment of this scientific-and-engineering potential in the very near future through the development of corresponding high-technology manufacturing of competitive products.

Legislative Changes

A number of important measures have been undertaken on the state level in order to improve state scientific-and-engineering politics. In particular, a new concept for the scientific-technological and innovative development of Ukraine has been adopted by the government, which envisages a more active state position in the scientific-technological sphere and increased incorporation of new knowledge and technologies in economics and other spheres. The concepts have been adopted under a new law "On the Scientific and Scientific-and-Engineering Activity." This new law will help to address a number of social problems for scientists. The Law of Ukraine "On the Priority Lines in the Development of Science and Engineering of Ukraine", adopted recently by the Verkhovna Rada, promotes forming new mechanisms for prognosticating scientific-and-engineering development, defining priorities in the development of science and engineering and their competitive financing. A number of legislative acts on intellectual property have also been adopted; Ukraine joined the corresponding international

agreements in this sphere. In particular, the ratification of the Agreement on the scientific-and-engineering cooperation between Ukraine and the USA took place in June of this year.

Ukraine is strengthening and developing its international contacts in the sphere of scientific-and-engineering activity. Such policies are finding positive response in many countries and with international organizations and foundations. Ukraine was very pleased when UNESCO asked it to host the International Workshop «The Role of International Organizations in the Development of All-European Space» earlier this year.

For Ukraine, these and other international scientific-industrial activities are important for the following reasons:

- to integrate Ukrainian science into the international scientific community;
- to attract investments into Ukraine's scientific-industrial sphere;
- to save the scientific-technological potential and scientific schools of Ukraine;
- to establish contacts between Ukrainian scientists and those of other countries;
- to transfer Ukrainian research and development (R&D) activities and technologies to the international market; and
- to participate in the international sharing of labor in the sphere of science and technologies.

All this proves that the scientific system of Ukraine stands before a new stage of its transformation, the stage of purposeful and controlled qualitative changes in the scientific and innovative systems.

A successful transformation of the national scientific system is possible for Ukraine, provided the realization of certain national strategic policies that support development of Ukraine's scientific and technological sphere. Among them the most important are:

First. A shift from the politics of *saving* to that of *restoring* the scientific potential in the sphere of fundamental research, in particular, scientific schools recognized in the world.

Second. A shift from the politics of passive observation to that of actively competing for a leading global position on new discoveries, implementation of "know-how" and new ideas. This will be attained by support of the corresponding applied research and design, and industrial high-end innovations.

Third. A shift from the "expending science" model to a model of real "commercializing of scientific knowledge". The adoption of intellectual property as the base for real economic growth will further promote this shift. It will help Ukraine move

toward a model of selling the products of intellectual labor, to introduce the objects of intellectual property into the economic trade, to create the background for the steady development of Ukraine in the 21st century.

I. Initial data for establishing a national scientific system in Ukraine

To better understand the preconditions for the formation of the national scientific system of Ukraine during the 90s, I will point out the main features of Ukraine's Soviet heritage.

1. *Political priorities.* Priorities required that scientific research and development be oriented towards keeping the Soviet Union as a world leader in the military sphere and that it be focused on developing heavy industry and military technologies.

2. *Centralized directive management.* Centralized control of research meant that huge amounts of material and financial and intellectual resources were focused on single scientific projects. The distribution of such resources as well as the determination of research priorities took place without any social input or competition.

3. *Coercion.* Coercion allowed for the forcible movement of significant people resources to perform large-scale projects. In addition, young scientists were distributed to fulfill the requirements of the planned economy.

4. *Normative planning of science as an economic branch.* This approach required planning of scientific work and research according to such criteria as volumes of labor, volumes of costs, volumes of provisions. A natural result is that payment for scientific labor did not depend on its scientific results.

5. *Closed society.* The closed nature of Soviet society gave rise to complete classification of scientific work and the establishment of secret scientific organizations. This environment also made it impossible for scientists work creatively abroad and limited free access for Ukrainian researchers to world intellectual achievements.

6. *System of privileges.* An administrative system of privileges and rewards for selected scientists existed.

7. *High social status of science.* Science was considered as the basic means for technical and social advance to build communism.

8. *Ideological set.* Social sciences became isolated from global development and served as a support for the state ideology.

It should be noted that the social status of researchers in the USSR was rather high. The state was simultaneously both a severe dictator and a relatively generous patron for science. Science itself played a double role of a beloved child and a bondman who serves. Until about the end of the 1980s, such features were typical for the scientific system in Ukraine as a part of the USSR; the system was functioning in an environment where administrative means, rather than economic means, controlled scientific and engineering activity.

A complicated hierarchical system was created to govern science: the party level (the corresponding departments of science in the Central Committee of the CPSU and Central Committees of the communist parties of the Union republics) – the state level (the State Committee of Science and Engineering of the USSR) – the All-Union branch Ministries and Committees – the republican branch Ministries and Committees – a scientific organization – scientific teams (departments, sectors, labors). According to this hierarchy, a vertical administrative distribution of material, financial and people resources took place.

The structure of the scientific system in the Soviet Union was also quite specific. It consisted of three scientific sectors, which corresponded to the economic branches. They were: the academic sector (the Academy of Sciences); the higher education sector (universities and polytechnic institutions); and the branch sector (research institutes, research and design, project and project-search organizations of branch subordination).

One scientific branch stood apart. It was the defense industry research sector. The evaluation of this sector is difficult due to the lack of corresponding statistics and the dual use character of civilian R&D work in civilian scientific organizations.

So, basic research was carried out primarily in the academic sector, applied research primarily in the higher education sector, and applied research for industrial purposes in the branch sector.

According to official statistics, until the time of the disintegration of the USSR, R&D in Ukraine was carried out in 1344 scientific organizations. Of those, 21.7% belonged to the academic sector, 10.8% to the higher education sector, and the remainder, to the branch sector. 450,000 people were engaged in science and engineering, of which 295,000 people directly carried out R&D work (researchers and technicians). 31,200 researchers possessed scientific degree of Doctor of Science or PhD. The average age for Doctors was 55 years and for PhDs – 47 years. 13,600 postgraduates should also be included in the total number of researchers. As potential researchers one should consider the students of higher schools amounting to 876,200 persons.

Until 1991, all R&D in Ukraine was funded by the state. The total budget in 1990 was 3.02% of the GDP. Most of those funds came from the state budget of the USSR; some also came from other state sources: the budgets of All-Union Ministries and Departments as well as from the republic's budget.

A specific feature of Ukrainian science under the USSR was the fact that Ukraine as a Union republic contributed only a very small part to financing its own scientific

potential. So, during the period 1989–1990, 90% of the total budget for Ukrainian science came from the budget of the USSR, and only 10% from the budget of Ukraine. Corresponding to the financial distribution, Ukraine's scientific potential was used primarily for the needs of the totalitarian state. There was almost no funding of science by independent foundations and organizations or by bank credits in the Soviet Union.

The political collapse and territorial disintegration of the USSR in 1991 led to the disintegration of the Soviet scientific system and to a fragmentation of the general scientific potential into pieces that were very unequal in their quantitative size and international scientific level.

At the same time, these phenomena are the starting point for a transitional process for the scientific system of Ukraine. The Ukrainian state began to independently take care of its own scientific potential.

II. Institutional-functional transformation of the national scientific system

The most important external factors that contributed to the reconstruction of Ukrainian science during the 1990s were: disintegration of the international socialist system of science; destruction of the system under which the state distributed R&D labor between the republics of the former USSR; a severe economic crisis and loss of priority of science in the new independent country's state politics.

In these new conditions, much of Ukraine's scientific potential, which had until then met the scientific needs of the entire USSR, appeared to be superfluous for just Ukraine. Prior to the disintegration of the USSR, Ukrainian scientific organizations carried out two thirds of work to fill external orders amounting to more than US \$1 billion. During the nineties, orders from the CIS countries decreased by a factor of 15. At the same time, science and engineering activity in the military branch decreased, after having made up more than 40% of Ukraine's R&D during Soviet times.

Three stages of transition are evident in the formation of a new scientific system in Ukraine.

The first stage was during the period 1991–1993. This stage consisted of a growing economic crisis and the transition from a regional scientific system into an independent one.

The change in social and economic conditions, a deep slow-down in production, a severe decrease in the gross domestic product, increasing inflation and state budget deficit, as well as a loss of status for science as the state priority caused a substantial decrease in financial support of science and engineering in Ukraine. The total costs for

R&D activity decreased for this period by a factor of 3.1 and as part of the GDP by a factor of 2.2. A mass outflow of scientific personnel caused the scientific-technological sphere of Ukraine to lose one fourth of its researchers. The number of students in high schools also decreased (6%) because many specialties were changed based on new social-economic conditions. New sources of finance for science and technology appeared: foreign customers, international foundations and organizations as well as the budgets of scientific organizations themselves. The proportion these sources of finance gradually began to rise and reached 11.5% in 1993.

The inflow of the youth into science substantially decreased. At the same time, researchers of the age from 40 to 55 left science and moved to new commercial spheres or went abroad.

Meanwhile, during this period, basic formal conditions were created to establish a national system of science of New Ukraine, namely:

- all scientific institutions located on Ukrainian territory were transferred to Ukrainian jurisdiction;
- initial legislative principles for maintaining and operating the scientific potential were formed;
- the scientific potential was applied to the goal of solving national social-economic and other problems through the identification of state science and engineering priorities, the creation of a system of science and engineering programs and projects, and implementation of competitive methods for R&D financing;
- a new institutional structure was formed: the government – the State Committee on Science and Engineering – branch ministries and committees, State Academies of Sciences – scientific organization – scientific teams (departments, sectors, labors));
- conditions were created for the activities of nongovernmental scientific institutions and new public scientific associations;
- social science started developing on the basis of internationally accepted methodological principles.

The second stage (1994–1998). This stage was characterized by a deepening of the changes from the first stage. The peculiarities of this stage were a substantial rise of infrastructural expenses; the absence of funds to pay salaries; and an almost complete reduction of funds for R&D in scientific organizations. Science and technology also suffered during this period from a decrease in orders from the industrial sector. The result of these conditions was both a real reduction in the number of researchers and a growth of latent unemployment in the scientific-technological sphere due to the forced introduction of a reduced workday. According to estimates, the level of latent unemployment in scientific organizations reached 60% and was one of the greatest

among all economic spheres of activities in Ukraine. The phenomenon of dual job holding by researchers, with the second job being in the commercial sector – grew during this time. As a result of these conditions, many scientific institutes, which were earlier supported by the state, came to the verge of closing. The percentage of R&D that was funded by the state government declined from 47% to 29%. At the same time, the percentage of financial support from the business sector and from foreign sources grew to 39% and 23%, respectively. Total financial support of R&D activity as part of the GDP in the nineties reached the lowest level of 1.16% (in 1996).

During this period, the scientific system could not compete in attracting young people with the economically attractive business sector. This caused a situation where, despite annual growth in the amount of students of higher educational institutions by 76,000 persons and postgraduates by 1,400 persons, the renovation of the scientific-and-engineering potential of Ukraine almost stopped. The average age of PhDs and Doctors of Science who stayed in the sphere of the scientific-and-engineering activities increased by 1 year for every 2–3 years. Simultaneously, the nongovernmental segment of Ukrainian science and technology was established and reached 15% by 1998.

The third stage started in 1999. Simultaneously with the economic recovery in production and the growth of GDP, Ukrainian science saw some weakening of negative trends. In particular, there was a stabilization of the number of researchers (41 researchers out of 10,000 workers in the economy). This number corresponds to the average European level. The number of Doctors of Sciences even began to grow. In the past two years we have seen a growth in completed scientific research and designs and in science and engineering production. The number of industrial enterprises which are engaged in innovation activity has begun to grow, as has yield of high-end production. This explains why Ukraine has kept its place among a small number of countries that possess their own science and engineering potential and are capable of high-end production, in particular in aviation and space design.

Substantial changes have been seen, in particular, in the whole sphere of social and humanitarian research. The fields of social science, political science, culture, archeology, and religion took their place as legitimate fields of study. In some leading academic institutes and national universities the volume of commercial research is increasing thanks to orders from industry. The processes of creating innovative structures, new for Ukraine, are continuing. These include territorial and branch innovative centers and industrial parks. The establishment of the market of intellectual property is taking place. And a mechanism to include intellectual property in a institute's assets is being developed. This is of extreme importance for the transfer of Ukrainian science to market conditions.

Ukraine has also seen the development of new information technologies, and with that have been considerable changes in the organization and employment of scientific information by Ukrainian researchers. The implementation of information technologies began with the process of accumulating, saving and spreading scientific information. For example, the Institute of Problems of Information Record (of NASU) and National V.I. Vernadsky Library of Ukraine started a project in 2000 of a nationwide Ukrainian abstract journal (UAJ) "Source". Simultaneously, in order to provide access to foreign periodicals, a project "Electronic Information for Libraries" is underway with support by the Foundation "Vidrodzhennya". The project is a joint enterprise of the Open Society Institute (Budapest) and the publishing house of periodics EBSCO, the greatest in the world.

The nongovernmental science and technology segment is being developed in Ukraine, and we have seen that the efficiency of scientific activity in the nongovernmental sector is higher than in state organizations. The main areas of activity in nongovernmental scientific organizations have become scientific design and rendering scientific services. Their percentage is growing every year and reached this year 35% of their total volume in Ukraine.

III. Analysis of the national scientific system: results from the decade of transformations

An analysis of the transition in the Ukrainian scientific sphere for the past 10 years enables us to define certain important social-economic and other conditions. These conditions have influenced the development of science and determined its effect on economics and on the solution of state-constitution problems.

First are the conditions needed to transform science in Ukraine from a regional into an independent national system. A decade ago, Ukraine's scientific system -- despite the presence of famous schools, prominent scientists and scientific achievements -- had a clearly regional character and in some branches, even a provincial character. Only one third of the scientific-and-engineering potential of Ukraine was used utilized toward Ukraine's interests. The volume of basic research amounted to only 8-9%, while major applied R&D was used for the needs of the military-industrial complex. This situation did not promote reconstruction of the national economy nor its effective development.

Only in the recent two years has the scientific system begun to resemble a system with the appropriate percentage of basic research, applied research, and designs. Those percentages are 13-14%; 22-23%; and 56-58%, respectively. The field of scientific services is developing quickly as well, its percentage increasing annually by 1-1.5%.

A second condition influencing the development of science has been that science has been gradually pushed from state priorities. This has meant a reduction of investments into science and the loss of innovative activity.

Although funding for research is at 1995-96 levels, the situation has stabilized and there has even been a steady growth in funding from the basic financial sources (state budget, enterprise sector and foreign customers).

More encouraging news is a legislative definition of science and engineering priorities in Ukraine up to 2006, as well as 30% budget allocation. This will promote fundamental changes in Ukraine's scientific sphere

A third general condition has been the change in state geopolitical tasks, the conversion of the military-industrial complex, and a new defense doctrine for Ukraine, all of which fostered changes in the motivation and reduction in financial support for military R&D. During Soviet times, almost one half of the scientific research budget was for the needs of the military-industrial complex. It is clear that this change in the direction of more than half of applied research has brought a substantial part of Ukrainian science into great financial straits.

Fourthly, Ukraine's scientific system was initially too strongly dependent on the state budget. With the decrease in orders from the industrial sector and inessential international support, the state has had to take up the role of the primary customer for R&D activities. This does not correspond to the requirements of a market economy.

Basic and applied research was separated from the real needs of the economy, and the scientific system as a whole and separate scientific teams lost the capability to objectively assess their work. This caused a lowering in the competitiveness of the research and undoubtedly influenced the level of Ukrainian product competitiveness.

The current indices of financial backing of research prove qualitative changes in Ukraine's contemporary scientific system, both in terms of its direction as well as the funding sources. So, the greatest percentage of financial support (38%) comes from the enterprise sector; the state budget investments total 30%; and the costs of foreign customers, international foundations and organizations amount to 23%. More than 90% of funding for basic research and 55% for applied research is provided by the state budget. At the same time, one third of investments for scientific designs are provided by foreign customers and more than 25% by the enterprise sector of the national economy.

The fifth condition I want to discuss is the exclusion of science from state priorities and the resulting social difficulties. Specifically, the decline of prestige of science as an attractive career, especially for talented youth. This negative trend presents

the greatest danger for Ukraine's domestic scientific potential. It affects our ability to save scientific schools and has led to an aging of Ukraine's scientific personnel. The average age of Doctors of Science is now 60 and PhDs is 51.

Simultaneously, positive changes are taking place. The inconsistency between the structure of scientific personnel in scientific branches and the new social-economic conditions formed since the beginning of the nineties caused fast growth (by factors of tens) in the number of postgraduates in political, legal and psychological specialties during 1991–2000. More than 18% of the total number of postgraduates are now becoming specialists in economics. And the total number of postgraduates has grown from 1991 to 2000 by a factor of 1.7. Such a strengthening promotes upgrading young researchers and partially compensates for the insufficient qualification of the youth for their activity in economic branches of the private sector.

Thus, the social-economic conditions during the 1990s under which the transformation of Ukraine's scientific system took place was in general not favorable for systematic positive change. The positive trends that have been achieved in this sphere are not yet stable as they depend on many factors, including the following:

- ◆ The basic driving forces of the Soviet system of organizing scientific activity have disappeared, while the institutions have partially remained.
- ◆ Science in Ukraine is still considered by the state to be a single branch of the economy, not as the base for innovative development of the economy as a whole. The attempts to reform the national scientific system "from above" have failed because they were carried out by changing the status of responsible agencies, not by taking a strategic view of development of science.

IV. Final theses and conclusions

The way of economic reforms, passed by Ukraine, has shown that the orientation only towards market means for the economy transformation, without state administration of the process of providing modern innovative level of production, is false. As a result, the economy has lost its renewable potential and has transformed into a redistributive economic system. Such an economy is incapable of solving the tasks of human welfare growth but, on the contrary, causes an exhaustion of material and spiritual forces of the people and retards normal reproduction of the nation.

Success in economic restructuring and continuation of the current economic recovery (for 2001 the growth in the GDP of Ukraine has reached above 10%) depend on the process of reforming the national scientific system. The establishment of a modern scientific system in Ukraine has been slowed by closure of R&D activity lines within separate scientific sectors; by attempts to concentrate R&D work in governmental

scientific organizations; and by the absence of real competition in scientific fields, mainly because of administrative distribution of state funds.

But the use of alternative financial sources, orientation of the best researchers towards the international scientific system through grants, primarily in basic research, leads us to hope that Ukraine's national scientific system will gradually become a real part of the world scientific system.

As an example we may note that during 1999–2000 Ukrainian researchers received more than 480 grants within the NATO program, second place in number only to Russia among the Euro-Atlantic Partnership Council countries. At the same time, in 2000–2001 Ukraine presents financial support to all those who received the NATO grant.

Ukraine is only at the beginning of a great path of integration into the global and European scientific community. Until it is recognized as an equal partner in scientific collaboration, Ukraine remains a provider of intellectual potential for other countries, more developed in the scientific and technological plane. We must work to prevent “brain drain” abroad and encourage researchers and specialists who have gone abroad to return to Ukraine. We must also invite and make it attractive for foreign specialists to carry out research at Ukrainian institutions, particularly those in fields where Ukraine possesses global achievements.